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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS THE MULTIPLE ASPECTS
OF MEDITATION FOR DIABETES CARE PROGRAMMES**¹Rahat Mustafa, ²Dr Rai Muhammad Toqeer Khan, ³Dr. Aleena Fayyaz¹University of Lahore, ²BHU 182 9L, Medical Officer, ³BHU Thatha Khero Matmal, Pindi Bhatiyani, Hafizabad.**Article Received:** December 2018**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

It is difficult to manage diabetes as it is a very complicated disorder and has many faces. Diabetes comes after the bio-psychosocial model of health. This research was held at Services Hospital, Lahore (February to November 2018). Healthy life should be maintained in order to manage diabetes. Moreover, evidence of chronic complexities and symptomatic comfort is also required. Thinking is one way that helps in maintaining a healthy life. The policies of thinking-based stress reduction in diabetes care, are illustrated by communication. In diabetes, these therapies hold an additional position.

Keywords: *Diabetes, Diabetes distress, Holistic health, Psychosocial.*

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INTRODUCTION:

A man is considered healthy if he is fit mentally socially and physically. Health is not just the absence of disorder. Therefore, it is a condition of peace of a person within himself as well as his contact with surrounding and society. For the health of a person, physical as well as psychosocial health should be considered as diabetes affect mental, emotional, psychological and social status of person [1]. Use of insulin, medication, controlling the comorbidities and complexities are involved in the management of diabetes.

Targeting psychological Stress in Diabetes:

Between the psychological discomfort and diabetes, the double association is found [2]. In the establishment of diabetes, heart-related disorders, hypertension and over-weight, the strong factor that is involved are negative mood, cognition and chronic stress. The element of depression, disorder regarding stigmatization and tensions are connected with diabetes [3]. So, reduction in stress helps a lot in the management of diabetes. The thing important in controlling diabetes distress are awareness and knowledge of patients, reduction of stress, the attention of family and clinician and hold in self-attention [2].

Meditation:

In older times, meditation is used for self-regulation of mind. In different cultures meditation has a different concept. It is a condition of steady attention and reflection and consideration. Its objective was to enhance emotional, spiritual and mental well-being. According to Shapiro and Walsh, meditation is defined as [M] meditation is an activity of self-regulation practices. These practices aimed at focusing on awareness and attention for the purpose of bringing

mental activities under self-control. Therefore, through this specific capacity like focusing clarity quietness etc. and normal mental well-being is encouraged [4].

The process of thinking has been helpful for self-improvement, minimizing stress and mental peace. A positive mental feature like focusing, quietness and coping strategies are promoted through it and negative attributes like depression anger, fear and anxiety are minimized. The major attention is given to mindfulness meditation in clinical psychology and health care all through many procedure meditations. Different things such as concentrating the mind on mantra, sound, breath, through or object with a non-judgmental knowledge of the current moment [5, 6].

Mindfulness meditation:

In order to control chronic diseases like depression, fibromyalgia, cancer, substance abuse, rheumatoid arthritis, chronic pain syndrome, anxiety eating disorders and heart-related disease, policies of mindfulness meditation like mindfulness-based stress reduction have been used in the psychology [7, 8]. The experiences of patients in chronic disease are affected by it and health attitudes are promoted by it. Mood, cognition, improved perception of well-being and development of positive coping skill has been enhanced through MBSR [8]. In many research studies anxiety, depression and common psychological distress in diabetic individuals have improved to a significant extent by using MBSR [9 – 11]. In other studies, weight and waist circumstances are minimized and improvement in blood pressure and glycaemia central with the activity mindfulness meditation are reported in minimizing the danger of heart-related disorders, meditation has been known as a supplement to pharmacological treatment and life style modification [15 – 17].

Table: Potential benefits of meditation in diabetes care

Biological exercise capacity	Reduced fatigue and improved
Reduced heart rate variability Reduced blood pressure	Weight reduction Improved glycemic control and Reduced anxiety and depression
Psychological	Stress reduction
Improvement in chronic pain and neuropathic symptoms Improved sleep	Improved self-esteem and self-control
Reduced loss of work days	Better inter-personal relationships Improved well-being and better quality of life
Health-related Behavior	Better acceptance of disease and comorbidities. Greater motivation and adherence to lifestyle modification and positive health behaviours. Greater adherence to monitoring and medication. A greater degree of self-control and self-reliance
Cessation of smoking, alcohol and substance abuse	Improved coping skills. Stronger patient-doctor relationship

Role of meditation in Diabetes Cares:

The policies of meditation did not offer extra expense and are beneficial to perception and reaction of a person to diabetes. Moreover, these policies are not complicated and easy to adopt. Self-control, behaviour related to health, self-reliance and quality of health is enhanced through it. Potential advantages in relation to the practice meditation in diabetes attention are enumerated in the given tabular data. It is not easy to train the mind. But it results in health and enjoyment.

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